

International Equity Portfolio Performance - to Hedge or not to Hedge Foreign Currency Risk

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Abstract: This study investigates whether hedging the currency risk improves portfolio performance. A total of 11 major foreign stock markets and their currencies as well as the U.S. stock market are included in the analysis. The Jensen, Sharpe, and Treynor measures are employed to compare the performance of hedged and unhedged portfolios constructed based on mean-variance portfolio optimization method. The results show that fully or partially hedging away currency risk improves the risk-return trade-off for international equity portfolios.

Keywords: International Equity Portfolio, Foreign Currency Risk, Jensen Measure, Sharpe Measure, Treynor Measure

1. Introduction

The role of foreign currencies in portfolio diversification for the US investors has been a popular topic for academicians as well as practitioners. This study sets out to seek answers to those questions in recent time period: Is hedging for the currency risk indeed beneficial for the overall portfolio return? Does hedging for the currency risk improve risk/return relation of the portfolio?

Modern portfolio theory is initially developed in the context of a closed economy (Markowitz, 1959; Tobin, 1958). Grubel (1968) expands the theory by introducing the notion of international diversification. This expansion results in a world welfare gain. A number of studies afterwards demonstrate the advantage of international diversification in terms of improved risk/return trade-off due to low correlations in stock returns among different markets (Levy and Sarnat, 1970; Bailey and Lim, 1992; Divecha et al., 1992; Speidell and Sappenfield, 1992).

Should investors hedge the exchange-rate risk in their investments in the global markets? Eun and Resnick(1985)is the first to systematically examine this question. Since then, it has been subject to active debate. Early studies find that for equity investments, the benefit from international diversification is enhanced by hedging the exchange-rate risk (for example, Eaker and Grant, 1985), Eun and Resnick(1985, 1988), and Soenen and Lindvall(1992)). Among them, Eun and Resnick(1985, 1988)find that hedging increases the Sharpe ratio of

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the portfolio; Eaker and Grant (1985) and Soenen and Lindvall (1992) find that hedging provides risk reduction but does not increase the return. These studies focus on developed countries. Thomas III (1989) documents similar results for internationally diversified bond portfolios. Hauser and Levy (1991) find that the correlation between the international and domestic bond returns and between the foreign bond and the currency returns are significantly lower for long-term than short-term bonds, indicating that more international diversification could be achieved by investing in long-term bonds. Glen and Jorion (1993) discover that over the period 1974-1990, hedging exchange risk results in statistically significant improvement in the Sharpe ratio for diversified portfolios containing equity and bonds.

Another stream of literature casts doubt on the benefit of hedging currency risk. Thomas III (1988) finds that exchange rate changes account for about 23% of the standard deviation of foreign equity returns during the 1975-1987 period. He also finds that unhedged foreign equity portfolios have a lower market risk (measured by beta) against the US market than the hedged ones; therefore, hedging away currency risk may not be optimal for the US investors as far as portfolio risk is concerned. Greco and Morey (1998) and Yang et al. (2006) point out that there are increased cross-market correlations among international equity markets, leading to less diversification effect. Using daily returns measured in the US dollar, Fooladi and Rumsey (2002) find that the correlation coefficients between the US equity market and 23 other equity markets do not increase during the 1988-2000 period. However, when the daily returns are measured in local currencies, the correlations do increase. During the same period, the correlations among the currencies (including the US dollar) decrease. Fooladi and Rumsey (2002) thus conclude that the benefits of international diversification still exist for the US investors as long as they do not hedge away currency risks because the two effects, namely, the increased correlations among equity markets and the decreased correlations among currencies, offset each other. Ratner et al. (2007) reach a similar conclusion; that is, including foreign currencies as one of the investment components improves the portfolio's Sharpe ratio. They believe the low correlation between the currencies and the equity markets creates this effect and thus, one should not hedge away currency risk.

As mentioned above, most of the early studies that find hedging to be beneficial focus on developed countries. Using equity return data from both developed and emerging markets, Hauser et al. (1994) find that hedging currency risk improves the mean-variance efficiency in developed but not in emerging stock markets. Using a data set that includes both segments of the markets, Ip (1991) shows that foreign exchange exposure can actually reduce both total as well as systematic risk for an investment. Chincarini (2007) finds that for the period 1984-2006, hedging currency risk may not improve the risk-adjusted returns

of a portfolio containing both segments of the markets, especially in a period of consistent home country currency depreciation; however, the overall volatility of the portfolio is reduced, albeit marginally.

In this study, we seek to answer the question of whether or not to hedge the currency risk for investments in the global environment. We use the optimization procedure to construct hedged and unhedged portfolios and compare them based on Jensen, Sharpe, and Treynor performance measures. However, we take one step further in that we employ statistical methods to test the difference in the performance measures. Compared to prior studies, our approach and results are thus more formal and scientific. The results show that in general, fully or partially hedging away currency risk improves the trade-off between risk and return for investments in international equity markets. The next section explains the data and the methodology. Section 3 analyzes the empirical results. Concluding remarks are given in Section 4.

2. Data and Methodology

In this study, a total of 12 major foreign stock markets and their currencies are included.¹ For each market we obtain the following data for the period of August 1997 to February 2019.

- 1) The foreign stock index monthly return measured in foreign currency (R_{FIFC});
- 2) The foreign currency monthly return measured in the US dollar (R_{FCD});
- 3) The foreign stock index monthly return measured in the US dollar (R_{FID}).

The investment in a foreign asset is comprised of two components: the foreign asset evaluated in foreign currency and the foreign currency evaluated in the US dollar. The foreign stock index return measured in the US dollar can be calculated based on the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_{FID} &= \left[1 + \frac{P_t - P_{t-1}}{P_{t-1}} \right] \left[1 + \frac{e_t - e_{t-1}}{e_{t-1}} \right] - 1 \\
 &= (1 + R_{FIFC})(1 + R_{FCD}) - 1
 \end{aligned}$$

where P_t is the foreign asset value at the end of month t , P_{t-1} is the foreign asset value at the end of month $t - 1$, e_t is the dollar value of the foreign currency at the end of month t , and e_{t-1} is the dollar value of the foreign currency at the end of month $t - 1$. In addition, the S&P500 monthly returns as well as the risk-free rates of return (represented by 3-month Treasury Bill monthly returns) for the same period are collected. Using mean-variance portfolio optimization method, the weight for each country in the portfolio is determined for

¹ They include the U. S., Japan, Australia, Brazil, Mexico, France, Germany, the Great Brittan, Italy, Canada, India and South Korea. China and Hong Kong are not included because their currencies are not free-floating.

each month, and then the weighted-average return for the month is calculated.

2.1. Portfolio Optimization

Suppose the market has a risk-free asset with return R_f and n risky assets. Let R_i be the random variable associated with the rate of return for risky asset i , for $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, and define the random vector $\boldsymbol{\mu} = (\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_n)^T$, where $\mu_i = E[R_i]$, and covariance matrix of returns of the assets $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$. When short selling is allowed, the minimum-variance portfolio with the expected return μ^* can be computed by solving the optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\boldsymbol{\omega}} \quad & \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\omega}^T \boldsymbol{\Sigma} \boldsymbol{\omega} \\ \text{subject to} \quad & \boldsymbol{\omega}^T \boldsymbol{\mu} + (1 - \boldsymbol{\omega}^T \mathbf{1}) R_f = \mu^* \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\omega} = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_n)^T$ is a set of weights associate with a portfolio, and $\mathbf{1} = (1, 1, \dots, 1)^T$, assuming that $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ is nonsingular and $\boldsymbol{\mu} \neq R_f \mathbf{1}$.

Using minimum-variance portfolio optimization method discussed above, the following international portfolios are formed:

- [1] All countries: all of the 12 countries are included. The portfolio optimization method is used to determine the weight for each country. Three portfolios are formed:
 - [1a] Completely hedged: R_{FIFC} is used for each country.
 - [1b] Completely unhedged: R_{FID} is used for each country.
 - [1c] Random hedge: either R_{FIFC} or R_{FID} is randomly selected for each country. Then, the optimization method is used to determine the weight for each country.
- [2] Random countries: each country is randomly selected. Then, the optimization method is used on the selected countries to determine the weight for each country. Three portfolios are formed:
 - [2a] Completely hedged: R_{FIFC} is used for each country.
 - [2b] Completely unhedged: R_{FID} is used for each country.
 - [2c] Random hedge: either R_{FIFC} or R_{FID} is randomly selected for each country. Then, the optimization method is used to determine the weight for each country.

We use 60-month rate of returns to estimate the optimal weights. Since the data start from August, 1997, the first 60-month period would be August 1997 to July 2002. We use this period's data to calculate the weights and the weighted-average return for August 2002. The data from the next 60-month period (that is, from September 1997 to August 2002) are used to calculate the next set of weights and the weighted-average return for September, 2002. This process is repeated until the last weighted-average return (for February 2019) is obtained.

2.2. Portfolio Performance Measures

Three portfolio performance measures are used to evaluate relative strategies performance: Jensen measure (Jensen, 1968), Sharpe measure (Sharpe, 1966), and Treynor measure (Treynor, 1965). The Jensen measure is the intercept from the regression of portfolio excess returns on the market portfolio excess returns:

$$R_{pt} - R_{ft} = \alpha_p + \beta_p (R_{mt} - R_{ft}) + \varepsilon_{pt}, \tag{2}$$

where R_{pt} is the portfolio return in month t , R_{ft} is the risk free return in month t , R_{mt} is the return on the market portfolio in month t , ε_{pt} is the error term, and α_p and β_p are the regression's intercept and slope coefficients, respectively. S&P500 return is used for the market factor in this study.

The Sharpe measure is defined by:

$$\frac{E[R_p] - R_f}{\sigma_p}$$

where $E[R_p] - R_f$ denotes the expected excess return of the portfolio, and σ_p denotes the standard deviation of portfolio return. This measures portfolio performance as the gain in returns corrected for standard deviation, which is the proxy of risk.

The Treynor measure is a measure of excess returns earned by a portfolio per unit of estimated equilibrium risk derived from traditional CAPM market model. Specifically, it is measured by:

$$\frac{E[R_p] - R_f}{\beta_p}$$

so that excess portfolio returns are divided by an estimated equilibrium risk $\beta_p = \frac{\sigma_{pm}}{\sigma_m^2}$, where σ_{pm} is the covariance between portfolio p and market portfolio m , and σ_m is standard deviation of market portfolio return.

For each portfolio, the portfolio performance measures are calculated as follows: for portfolio [1], we calculate expected monthly returns and performance measures for each portfolio. For portfolio [2], once each country is randomly selected, we calculate portfolio expected monthly returns and performance measures, and then such a process is repeated 500 times to obtain 500 Jensen, Sharpe, and Treynor measures, respectively.

2.3. Hypothesis Testing with the Performance Measures

The Jensen measure implies the share of additional return due to the portfolio manager's choices, based on the CAPM (Capital Asset Pricing Model) developed by Sharpe (1964). The statistical significance of the measure α_p can be evaluated by the t-statistic of the

regression model (2) above. To compare the Jensen performance measures of portfolio [1], we examine the significance of α_p and its magnitude. The Sharpe and Treynor measure, however, cannot be used for relative comparisons on a statistical basis since $E[R_p]$, σ_p , and β_p are unknown in general and should be replaced by their sample estimates. Jobson and Korkie (1981) present a derivation of the asymptotic distribution of Sharpe and Treynor measure. Their test (hereafter JK test) examines the significance of the difference in the performance measures between two portfolios. Thus, for two portfolio i and j , the following null hypothesis is tested for Sharpe measure:

$$H_0: Sh_{ij} = Sh_i - Sh_j = \sigma_j \mu_i - \sigma_i \mu_j = 0$$

where μ_i and μ_j are the mean excess returns above the risk-free rate of return on portfolio i and j , respectively. σ_i and σ_j are the standard deviations of portfolios i and j , respectively. Sh_{ij} indicates the difference between the Sharpe measures of the portfolios i and j (Sh_i and Sh_j). The sample estimator of the difference between those Sharpe measures is given by:

$$\hat{Sh}_{ij} = s_j r_i - s_i r_j$$

where r_i and r_j are the sample estimates of μ_i and μ_j , respectively. s_i and s_j are the sample estimates of σ_i and σ_j , respectively. It is noted that the estimator \hat{Sh}_{ij} is normally distributed with mean Sh_{ij} and variance θ_{ij} defined as follows:

$$\theta_{ij} = \frac{1}{T} \left[2\sigma_i^2 \sigma_j^2 - 2\sigma_i \sigma_j \sigma_{ij} + \frac{1}{2} \mu_i^2 \sigma_j^2 + \frac{1}{2} \mu_j^2 \sigma_i^2 - \frac{\mu_i \mu_j}{2\sigma_i \sigma_j} (\sigma_{ij}^2 + \sigma_i^2 \sigma_j^2) \right].$$

For the Treynor measure, we test the hypothesis on the sample difference:

$$H_0: \hat{T}r_{ij} = \hat{T}r_i - \hat{T}r_j = \frac{s_{jm} r_i}{s_m^2} - \frac{s_{im} r_j}{s_m^2} = 0$$

where s_{im} and s_{jm} are sample covariance between portfolio i and market portfolio and between portfolio j and market portfolio, respectively. s_m is the sample estimate of σ_m . The asymptotic distribution is normal with mean Tr_{ij} and variance

$$\psi_{ij} = \frac{1}{T} [\sigma_i^2 \sigma_{jm}^2 + \sigma_j^2 \sigma_{im}^2 - 2\sigma_{im} \sigma_{jm} \sigma_{ij} + \mu_i^2 (\sigma_j^2 \sigma_m^2 - \sigma_{jm}^2) + \mu_j^2 (\sigma_i^2 \sigma_m^2 - \sigma_{im}^2) - 2\mu_i \mu_j (\sigma_{ij} \sigma_m^2 - \sigma_{im} \sigma_{jm})].$$

In portfolio [2], on the other hand, since we have 500 Jensen, Sharpe, and Treynor measures from random selections for each portfolio, we use the Kruskal-Wallis test (hereafter KW test), one of non-parametric methods, to test whether computed measure originates from the same distribution.

3. Empirical Results and Analysis

To see whether hedging away currency risk improve portfolio performance, the following comparisons are made. The portfolio number is in square bracket.

Comparison 1: portfolios [1a] vs. [1b];

Comparison 2: portfolios [1b] vs. [1c];

Comparison 3: portfolios [2a] vs. [2b];

Comparison 4: portfolios [2b] vs. [2c].

Table 1(a) provides portfolio performance measures over the time period, August, 2002 to February, 2019. The test statistics for the comparisons and their statistical significances are reported on Table 1(b). The test statistics for Comparisons 1 and 3 indicate that the completely hedged portfolio outperforms the completely unhedged portfolio, and those for Comparisons 2 and 4 reveal that the partially hedged portfolio outperforms the unhedged portfolio when the countries included in the portfolio are randomly selected.

Table 1: Whole Sample Period: August 2002 to February 2019

(a) Portfolio Performance Measures							
	All Countries [1]			Random Countries [2]			S&P
	Completely Hedged [1a]	Completely Unhedged [1b]	Random Hedged [1c]	Completely Hedged [2a]	Completely Unhedged [2b]	Random Hedge [2c]	
Jensen	0.0187**	0.0033	0.0043	0.1627	0.0171	0.0178	
Sharpe	0.1904	0.0225	0.0435	0.0626	0.0308	0.1185	0.1261
Treynor	0.031	0.0125	0.0114	0.0406	0.0266	0.0323	0.0051
(b) Test Statistics							
	JK Z -Statistics		KW Rank Sum Test: χ^2				
	[1a] and [1b]	[1b] and [1c]	[2a] and [2b]	[2b] and [2c]			
Jensen			38.147***	5.6419**			
Sharpe	2.1063**	1.1395	49.521***	213.01***			
Treynor	3.1517***	0.1785	20.854***	32.525***			

Note: Expected monthly returns and performance measures are calculated for each portfolio in portfolio [1]. In portfolio [2], once each country is randomly selected, the portfolio expected returns and performance measures are calculated, and then such a process is repeated 500 times to obtain 500 Jensen, Sharpe, and Treynor measures, respectively. The expected return μ^* in Equation (1) is set to 3%. ***, ** and * denote statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels respectively.

Table 2 and 3 show the portfolio performance measures and their test statistics for the two sub-periods, August 2002 to December 2008 and January 2009 to February 2019,

respectively. The world equity markets reach their bottom in 2008 due to the financial crisis. The aforementioned examinations are repeated for each period. The results for the first period, August 2002 to December 2008, shown in Table 2, are essentially the same as those in Table 1. Over the second period, January 2009 to February 2019, hedging away currency risk does not provide benefit when all countries are included in the portfolio construction, as the results from Comparisons 1 and 2 show. However, when the countries included are randomly selected, the benefit is present, as the results from Comparisons 3 and 4 show. Overall, hedging away currency risk enhance portfolio performance over the sample period.

Table 2: Sub-sample Period: August 2002 to December 2008

(a) Portfolio Performance Measures							
	All Countries [1]			Random Countries [2]			S&P
	Completely Hedged [1a]	Completely Unhedged [1b]	Random Hedged [1c]	Completely Hedged [2a]	Completely Unhedged [2b]	Random Hedge [2c]	
Jensen	0.0325**	0.0189	0.0218*	0.1863	0.0358	0.0451	
Sharpe	0.2798	0.1432	0.1748	0.1221	0.0609	0.1772	-0.0445
Treynor	0.1239	0.0223	0.0185	0.128	-0.0025	0.0072	-0.0019
(b) Test Statistics							
	JK Z-Statistics		KW Rank Sum Test: χ^2				
	[1a] and [1b]	[1b] and [1c]	[2a] and [2b]	[2b] and [2c]			
Jensen			16.715***	41.285***			
Sharpe	1.8240*	0.7565	74.292***	239.32***			
Treynor	20.6826***	0.6322	53.353***	72.606***			

Note: Expected monthly returns and performance measures are calculated for each portfolio in portfolio [1]. In portfolio [2], once each country is randomly selected, the portfolio expected returns and performance measures are calculated, and then such a process is repeated 500 times to obtain 500 Jensen, Sharpe, and Treynor measures, respectively. The expected return μ^* in Equation (1) is set to 3%. ***, ** and * denote statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels respectively.

Table 3: Sub-sample Period: January 2009 to February 2019

(a) Portfolio Performance Measures							
	All Countries [1]			Random Countries [2]			S&P
	Completely Hedged [1a]	Completely Unhedged [1b]	Random Hedged [1c]	Completely Hedged [2a]	Completely Unhedged [2b]	Random Hedged [2c]	
Jensen	0.0074	-0.0027	-0.0028	0.0051	-0.0025	-0.003	
Sharpe	0.1602	0.005	0.0056	0.0607	0.0323	0.1138	0.2434
Treynor	0.017	0.0044	0.0043	0.0138	-0.0328	0.0108	0.0094

Table 3 continued

(b) Test Statistics				
	JK Z-Statistics		KW Rank Sum Test: χ^2	
	[1a] and [1b]	[1b] and [1c]	[2a] and [2b]	[2b] and [2c]
Jensen			6.3031**	19.807***
Sharpe	1.4564	0.0697	23.386***	138.94***
Treynor	1.5144	0.03	0.5841	8.6026***

Note: Expected monthly returns and performance measures are calculated for each portfolio in portfolio [1]. In portfolio [2], once each country is randomly selected, the portfolio expected returns and performance measures are calculated, and then such a process is repeated 500 times to obtain 500 Jensen, Sharpe, and Treynor measures, respectively. The expected return μ^* in Equation (1) is set to 3%. ***, ** and * denote statistical significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels respectively.

4. Concluding Remarks

This study seeks to answer the question of whether or not to hedge away currency risk for investments in the global environment. Our results show that hedging improves portfolio performance over the period from August, 2002 to February, 2019, when the portfolios are formed based on mean-variance optimization method. Based on Jensen, Sharpe, and Treynor measures, the fully hedged and partially hedged portfolios outperform the unhedged portfolios in terms of risk/return trade-off. This finding is consistent with those of Eun and Resnick (1985 and 1988) and Glen and Jorion (1993), while they only examine Sharpe measure but not the Jensen and Treynor measures. Although the findings from Thomas III (1988), Greco and Morey (1998), Yang et al. (2006), Fooladi and Rumsey (2002), Ratner et al. (2007), and Hauser et al. (1994) cast doubt on the benefit of hedging, which is contrary to our findings, their sample periods are not the same as ours.

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